

THE RUSSIAN SPACE PROGRAM POST 1991

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ABSTRACT

Since the collapse of the Soviet Union in 1991, the Russian space program has undergone dramatic transformation amid political, economic, and institutional upheaval. This paper traces its evolution from a Cold War era superpower to a space actor navigating financial instability, international cooperation, and internal reform. It explores the shift from the Soviet legacy structures to the establishment of Roscosmos and the commercialization of the Russian space program through international collaboration, notably with NASA for the construction and operation of the International Space Station (ISS). However, Russia's space ambitions have been curtailed by economic sanctions and geopolitical isolation due to the annexation of Crimea in 2014 and the full-scale invasion of Ukraine in 2022. The war has isolated Russia from Western cooperation, forcing a strategic shift towards the East, while the Russian space program relies solely on domestic resources and technology. Despite facing severe budget constraints, corruption, and technological stagnation, Russia persists in asserting its presence through strategic projects and symbolic missions. This paper argues that the Russian space program, while diminished from its Soviet heights, remains a politically charged instrument of state power, shaped as much by conflict and ideology as by scientific pursuit.

KEYWORDS

Russia, Space, commercialization, crisis, cooperation, war, security, satellites, sanctions.

1. A challenging start

Following the dissolution of the Soviet Union, Russia took over management of the former Soviet space program. Through a government decree, the Russian Federal Space Agency (RKA), later to be known as Roscosmos, was formed on the 25th of February 1992, with Yuri Koptev, placed in charge.

Under the new structure, the newborn agency oversaw the entire space program, contrary to the Soviet model in which the design bureaus handled their own initiatives, receiving governmental approval later. However, the NPO Energia was still behind the manned space program, providing it with rockets, spacecraft, and personnel. Energia eventually became a privately traded company named “Russian Space Corporation (RSC) Energia” due to the fact that it had to generate its own revenue in order to keep all the projects around Mir alive, despite the major budgetary cuts. Similarly, some other supporting bureaus which provided hardware were also privatized.¹

The decline of the Russian space program had already begun in the late Soviet era. In 1987, the Soviet space program numbered up to 400,000 employees in the assembly lines in Moscow, in rocket factories in Dnepropetrovsk and Kyubyshev, in scientific institutes all around the country, as well as in production plants and the tracking network. A year later, in 1988, the Secretary General announced in a Party conference the introduction of two policies: glasnost (openness) and perestroika (reform). For the first time in decades, Soviet citizens were provided with the right to speak freely and openly. Although it seemed a beneficial reform for the Soviet society, concerning the space program it had the opposite effect. During the 1989 elections, candidates supporting budget cuts to the space program were elected, threatening the stability of the space activities. Indeed, in April 1990, the government proposed cuts to the Soviet space budget around R300m and R220m.

The Soviet space shuttle, Buran, took the highest toll, as it saw its second autonomous flight being pushed back to 1992, although it was obvious that it would later be cancelled. This led to many workers leaving the sheds of the Baikonur cosmodrome in which the Buran mission was being prepared. The list of the delayed projects was also filled with the upcoming Mars mission, Mars 94, as it was pushed back two years, along with other projects like Spektr observatory. Other planned planetary and asteroid missions were completely erased from the launch schedule. In the meantime, the dissolution of the Soviet Union took place in 26th December 1991. In January 1st 1992, it was replaced by the Russian Federation and the Commonwealth of Independent States (CIS).

The newly formed Russian Federation was struggling from the beginning to keep the space program on track both administratively and financially. As the Soviet Union was

falling apart, cosmonauts Sergei Krikalev and Aleksandr Volkov remained on board Mir unbothered as members of the ongoing mission Soyuz TM-13, but were still affected by the chaos that was unfolding on Earth. Krikalev was especially disadvantaged, since he was forced to extend his stay on Mir by almost six months, doubling the duration of his mission – Soyuz TM-12 – which was raised to ten months in total (311 days), posing risks to his health condition due to exposure to space radiation, muscle atrophy –an effect of weightlessness– etc. This was because the next mission, Soyuz TM-13, consisted of only one career cosmonaut, Aleksandr Volkov, with the other two seats being occupied by Austrian researcher Franz Viehböck (privately funded seat) and the Kazak Toktar Aubakirov, who was sent to Mir in order to keep the relations with the soon to be independent Kazakhstan harmonious. The Baikonur cosmodrome, on which the space program was heavily dependent, was located in Kazakhstan. Thus, there was no available seat for Krikalev to return to Earth, except the Randuga re-entry capsule attached to Mir which Krikalev chose not to use.² When both cosmonauts returned to Earth on March 25, 1992, they were named “The last Soviet citizens” as their spacesuits still had the Soviet flag on them.³

2. The road to commercialization

Commercial expeditions to Mir space station had already initiated from 1990 and the mission Soyuz TM-10⁴ carrying cosmonauts Gennady Manakov, Gennady Strekalov and the Japanese TV reporter Toyohiro Akiyama, the first full paying visitor, whose week-long trip was paid for by the Japanese Tokyo Broadcasting System. It was one of the most effective ways to bring in the very needed foreign currency to the fiscally stressed Russian economy. Other measures included auctions of rare space history items, the filming of advertisements on Mir, and paid tours to the cosmonauts training centers. Astronauts from France and Germany flew to Mir on paid seats financially backed by their national space agencies and the European Space Agency (ESA). The cost of each seat varied from 12 million US Dollars up to 40 million, depending on the duration of each mission and its complexity. Those funds were under the control of the Energiya Corporation, the new Mir owner.⁵

The following year, 1993, the Energiya Buran program was formally cancelled, throwing into the waste bin almost twenty years of hard work of the country’s best design bureaus and scientists, that produced only one autonomous Buran flight, accompanied by just two launches of the most powerful rocket of the time, Energiya. The loss of almost 30% of the space program’s total workforce, at the same year, came as a consequence. However, in April 4th, Presidents Clinton and Yeltsin released a statement⁶ for US – Russian cooperation in space, and in December of the same year, the United States officially invited Russia to become a full partner in the creation of the International Space Station (ISS), based mainly on Russian hardware and US funds. Russia accepted the proposal and, to pave the path to the ISS, the nations also agreed to establish a joint

program for the operation of the Mir space station that included the launch of US astronauts and shuttle missions to the space station in exchange for good practices and to build mutual trust. This was the Shuttle – Mir program, also known as “Phase One”.⁷ The construction of the ISS would be “Phase Two”. By joining their forces, both nations managed to strengthen their presence in space while simultaneously canceling out each other’s weaknesses: lack of extended space missions for the US and lack of funding for Russia. Thus, the space race that had begun in the 50’s, was effectively terminated. In the private sector, the companies Lockheed Martin (LM), Khrunichev and Energia formed a joint company, the International Launch Services (ILS) which went into operation in 1995 as a private spaceflight partnership, initially co-marketing exclusively non-military launches on both the American Atlas and the Russian Proton expendable launch vehicles.⁸

In the interim, the financial situation of the Russian space sector was still deteriorating. By the end of 1994, employment was down to less than 300,000 people. Space spending was down to 0.23% of the national budget, compared to 0.97% spent on space research in the United States. On the subject of spending, employees in space companies were left unpaid for months, some of them were effectively bankrupt, subcontractors denied the delivery of components and fuel to conduct rocket launches unless their contracts were paid off, and the military and unmanned space activities were in decline. Infrastructure in Baikonur and in Plestsek cosmodromes as well as in other space related facilities was also not in a passable state. Buildings suffered from neglect and lack of maintenance. The results involved blackouts, destroyed launch pads that were not fixed, malfunctioning air conditioning systems in offices, and uncollected trash. Eventually, in 1996 for the first time since the 60’s the United States launched more rockets into space than Russia. Nonetheless, on Mir space station, two separate events, a fire onboard the Spektr module and a crash with a remotely controlled, by the Mir crew, cargo ship threatened the peaceful coexistence of the United States and Russia, highlighting the diverging approach of the two space powers concerning safety standards in space activities.⁹

By reaching its lowest point, the rebirth of the Russian space program was in fact a matter of time. Besides the agreement with the United States for the ISS, the Russian authorities also made deals with the European partners. A joint company, Starsem, was set up in July of 1996, as a part of an agreement between the TsSKB Progress plant in Samara and the French Arianespace company, with the mission of developing and commercially marketing the Soyuz rocket. Starsem’s shares were divided between EADS – 35%, the Russian Space Agency – 25%, TsSKB Progress – 25%, and Arianespace – 15%. Starsem also provided the necessary funds to restore facilities at Samara and Baikonur, including rocket assembly halls, payload separation facilities, and a staff’s hotel.¹⁰ At the dusk of the 20th century, Russia was on its way to recover from the financial recession and the effects of the collapse of the Soviet Union on its space program.

Figure 1: Annual number of objects launched into space. Source: <https://ourworldindata.org/grapher/yearly-number-of-objects-launched-into-outer-space?time=1992..1999&focus=RUS~USA>

3. Russia in the dawn of the 21st century

By 2000, an organized system of commercial space tourism was introduced, working through the American company Space Adventures, with a standard price of 20 million dollars per mission. Simultaneously, seats were sold to the European Space Agency (ESA) or to national space agencies in Europe or combinations of the two. By 2001, 87 Russian space companies had entered joint ventures with American and European companies, leading to a visible flow of new money into the program. In a decade, Russia had managed to convert the most centralized space program to the most commercial, globally connected space industry in the world.

In the early 2000's, Russia's space ambitions were rising similarly to the rise of the oil prices. Once again, the Russian economy was flooded with foreign currency, fueling the country's industry, including the space one. In 2005, the Russian space strategy was published, complimented by President Putin's remarks that in order to achieve global leadership, strength in space was necessary. The proposed commercial and civilian plans comprised of a new space station, a return to the moon, new launch systems and robotic

exploration. Another economic crisis however, that of 2008, obliged the Russian aspirations in space to subside, causing also irregularities to Proton and Soyuz launches. In regard to the military part of the space program, Russia has been transparent about its national goal to exploit outer space as a military asset, as well as preventing the United States from being benefited by space activities for security reasons.¹¹ The Sino-Russian proposal of the Prevention of Placement of Weapons in Outer Space Treaty (PPWT) in 2002, is an example of this two-sided strategy, despite the fact that the Russian national strategy considered outer space and information sectors to be developed as new warfare areas. In general, the concept of the militarisation of space shares the same perception with the Soviet era, regarding it as a way to protect the Russian extensive borders and all the critical facilities which are scattered all over the country by creating a “protection zone” above the Russian soil.¹²

Thus, during the 00’s Russia began restructuring its space industry, with Space and defence industries rerouting their production away from export markets and towards national armed forces. Direct ascent anti-satellite weapons (DA-ASAT), the restoration of the Global Navigation System (GLONASS), and the launch of various satellites such as those for Intelligence, Surveillance and Reconnaissance (ISR), are amongst the Russian investments in military capabilities. On top of that, on April 21, 2007, an "operational meeting" of the Security Council of the Russian Federation approved a "System of views for Russia's independent access to space from its own territory for the full spectrum of tasks until 2040." By the end of the year, Russia made the potentially momentous decision to develop a new launch facility for manned missions in the nation's Far East, and on November 6, President Putin signed a decree on the creation of the Vostochny (= Eastern)¹³ launch site in the Amur Region, planning to make Vostochny the main Russian spaceport thus making the Russian space program and its access to space fully independent from third countries (Kazakhstan in this case).¹⁴

It was the war in Georgia in 2008 that resulted in the formation of first cracks in the Russian relations with the West by abandoning the proposed plans for a common lunar booster for future expeditions. Under Medvedev’s presidency the Russian economy managed to handle successfully the global economic crisis that year, mainly thanks to government subsidies. The conflict in Georgia revealed the limits of the Russian military capabilities along with the failure of the command-and-control system. As a result, the Russian leadership realized the need to invest more in space-based systems as highly important and essential for integration of command, control, communications, information, surveillance and reconnaissance (C3ISR). Furthermore, the ‘information-strike operations’ were introduced, which consist of ‘information-strike battles, information-weapons engagements and strikes with the goal of disrupting enemy troop command and control of weapons systems and the destruction of its information resource.¹⁵

4. The second decade: 2010 – 2022

Undoubtedly, the annexation of Crimea is be considered as the turning point for Russia's relations with the West. The sanctions against Russia that began in 2014 as a result of the invasion of Ukraine led to restrictions on technological trade and scientific exchanges between the West and Russia, along with a long-term, contractual, launch embargo on nearly 200 Russian civil-space and commercial satellites.¹⁶ Furthermore, the budget of the Russian Space Program has been gradually reduced since then as a consequence of these sanctions.¹⁷ As the tensions raised, Russia's military doctrine called included the launch of weapons in space to station in orbit, making the Russian forces capable of achieving a global strike at any moment needed.

Moreover, the Russian military and space strategy have the United States as their driving force, by always seeking counter measures to lower the US capabilities and their efficiency, as this seems the only way for Russia to maintain the strategic balance with the USA. In this matter, counter-space activities, especially cyber and electronic warfare play a central part in Russian strategy. However, after the retirement of the Space Shuttle in 2011, they only way to launch astronauts and cosmonauts to the ISS was by the Russian Soyuz spacecraft, until NASA's SpaceX Crew-1 mission in 2020.¹⁸

The submission by China and Russia in 2014, of the renewed version of their draft Treaty on the PPTW, fosters the opinion that the Russian Federation's diplomatic strategy is in compliance with the United Nation's context, probably in a quest to maintain a key role in the shaping of the global security architecture, especially in a multipolar international system.¹⁹

During this decade, the Russian space program and capabilities kept growing. The first launch from the new Vostochny cosmodrome took place in 2016. At the same year, the new National Security Strategy was introduced replacing the one of 2010. Also, Roscosmos, was transformed from a stage agency to a state company in an attempt to boost its performance and to combat corruption within the organization and in 2017 Russia announced a decrease in space launch incidents from 6.9% in 2015, to 4.7%. In 2019 and 2020, the country tested prototype space weapons, soliciting protests from the United States and others.²⁰ Once again in 2021, Russia drew the attention of the international community during a DA-ASAT weapon test which generated approximately 1.500 pieces of debris posing a threat to the integrity of the ISS and its cosmonauts onboard.²¹

5. Russia in space after 2022

Once more, the Russian space program took a sharp turn, this time as a result of the full-scale invasion of Ukraine on 24 February 2022. In a sense, Russia now had to put in practice the doctrines and the weapons tested during the previous decade. The effects of this invasion however, were immediate, severe, multinational and multileveled.

Orbital launches plummeted to just 22 in 2022, as companies like the UK's OneWeb, looked for other means of launching their payloads, through SpaceX and India, concluding

any further international cooperation with the Russian authorities in space due to the posed sanctions. In the same manner, ESA suspended in March 2022, the launch of the ExoMars Rover and Surface Platform mission that was scheduled for September 2022, seeking for other means of launching this mission.²² Despite the hostile relations with the United States, the two nations coexistence in the ISS and the need to launch crewed missions to the space station, have prevented the complete cut off of their relations, limiting their interactions to the absolute necessary.²³ In respect to China, the proposed collaboration in space stalled too. Initially, China had announced a joint project in 2021 to construct an International Lunar Research Station (ILRS) with Russia, however, its 2022 national space strategy did not even mention Russia, and Beijing refused to host Russian cosmonauts on board the Tiangong space station,²⁴ announcing in March 2025 the intention to train and later host Pakistani astronauts onboard the Tiangong Space Station.²⁵ On his side, President Putin welcomed the North Korean leader Kim Jong Un to the Vostochny cosmodrome in September 2023, seeking military cooperation with North Korea in the context of “a fight against imperialism” as Kim Jong Un stated himself.²⁶ Indeed, in fall of 2024, North Korea reportedly sent military personnel to Russia who fought against Ukraine for Russia in Russian uniforms and under Russian command.

6. Russian space activities during the Russo-Ukrainian war

In many occasions, the Russo-Ukrainian war is characterized as a future warfare and not in vain. On February 24, one hour prior to the Russian invasion of Ukraine, a cyberattack was launched on the American satellite company Viasat. Russian hackers launched destructive “wiper” malware called AcidRain against Viasat modems and routers, quickly erasing all the data on the system. The machines then rebooted and were permanently disabled. Approximately, 4000 modems in all zones of operation of the KA-SAT satellite, notably Ukraine, were effectively deemed unusable. The decision to attack Viasat was of course not random: Viasat works with the US military and its partners around the world. *“The attack has turned out to be typical of the “hybrid” war strategy employed by Moscow”*, say experts.²⁷ This cyberattack complemented the invasion by ground forces on the field, demonstrating the fact that in the modern warfare the conflicts are multilayered and the cyber sector’s role and significance is growing. Just a few hours before, Russian hackers used another wiper, called HermeticWiper, against Ukrainian government computers. In this case, the targets were Windows machines on networks that would be important for the government in Kyiv to mount an effective resistance in the early hours of the invasion. A second cyberattack against Viasat followed, disrupting the connection between government and military bodies as well as the access of Ukrainian households and public infrastructure to the internet.

Russia also has some dependence on space capabilities for its warfighting. For example, the Russian GLONASS system is a constellation of precision, navigation, and timing (PNT) satellites which provide Russia with its own GPS-like capability. On field, it delivers PNT services for commercial aircraft, military navigation and weapons guidance.

Although the GLONASS system is supposed to guide weapons to long-range target with high accuracy, in reality, the incomplete and aged GLONASS constellation has been unable to fulfill its mission, causing Russian rockets to miss their targets in Ukraine by a large margin in some cases.²⁸ The Western sanctions, already in effect since 2014, have hampered maintenance, upgrade and introduction of new space hardware by Russia. Another example of Russia's limited operational readiness and effectiveness, is the failure of the Luna-25 mission, carrying Russia's lunar lander.²⁹

The limited in quantity orbital hardware, is not the only issue affecting the Russian space program. Until 2023, the country counted for 160 satellites in orbit, of which more than 100 are military equipment, including 25 GLONASS satellites, 47 communications satellites, 7 Liana oceanic electronic reconnaissance satellites, and others. However, it is noted that Russia doesn't possess neither the proper mix of satellites, nor the suitable ground systems and procedures to work on, and benefit from the data transmitted by those satellites. As an example, the Liana spacecraft has been designed to track ships and US aircraft carriers in the Pacific Ocean. Thus, Liana spacecraft has little effect in the Ukrainian ground war.³⁰

On the other side, the one of the Electronic War, Russia has made some accomplishments, in the direction of reducing Ukraine's benefits from space capabilities. The US launched and operated Starlink system has been the prime target of the Russian actions. It is due to the heavy reliance of the Ukrainian forces on Starlink for battlefield communications, and on its ability to help coordinate devastating artillery strikes, that Russia has been looking for ways to disable it through jamming or by attacking it. By jamming Starlink satellites and the GPS receivers, Russians manage to "blind" Ukrainian drone operators and the Ukrainian artillery, who are unable to fulfill their missions.³¹ Especially for the second, Ukraine has received an increasing and substantial quantity of High Mobility Artillery Rocket Systems (HIMARS) and Joint Direct Attack Munitions (JDAMs) from the US. In fact, Starlink satellites are so popular at the Russo-Ukrainian battlefield, due to the fact that they possess an unmatched advantage in comparison to the High Earth Orbit satellites: Operating constellations on Low Earth Orbit (LEO) makes it more difficult, if not impossible, to take them offline because an attacker would have to target all the satellites at once, to disable the entire system. Also, it is cheaper and easier to set up a constellation on LEO, and in large numbers.³²

Since the invasion of Ukraine, in order to improve its ISR capabilities, Russia has launched a series of satellites: In August 9, 2022, the Russian made, Iranian Khayyam 1³³ Earth observation satellite was launched by Russia for government and military use. Yet, the Russian officials announced the intention to not deliver the satellite to Iran immediately, as Russia intended to use it in order to enhance its surveillance of military targets in the Ukrainian war.³⁴ The Russian Lotos-S1 (14F145) satellites, which are part of the next generation ELINT satellite system "Liana". From April 4, 2022, Russia has launched four Lotos satellites. Lotos-S1 No. 5,6,7,8.³⁵ The Razbeg (14F169) satellites, which are small military optical reconnaissance satellites similar to the Iranian Khayyam.

They were launched in December 27, 2023 and in February 2, 2024.³⁶ Then, the Uragan-K2 (GLONASS-K2, 14F160) navigation satellites, the upgraded versions of Uragan-K (GLONASS-K) satellites, that also carry classified military payload. They were launched in August 7, 2023, and in March 2, 2025.³⁷ Also, the civil Earth observation satellites Resurs-P 4 and 5 (47KS), capable of acquiring high-resolution imagery (up to 1m), which are used for defense purposes too. They were launched in March 31, 2024 and in December 25, 2024.³⁸ Finally, the classified military satellites labeled as Kosmos 2581, 2582 and 2583, launched in February 5, 2025, with an unknown purpose.³⁹

7. Conclusions and future prospects

The Russian space program has been dealing with challenges even before the collapse of the Soviet Union. The economic recession of the first decade after the creation of the Russian Federation, left its footprint on the integrity and effectiveness of the Russian space program in terms of the state of the existing infrastructure and hardware, as well as the operational readiness. In a sense, Russia was forced to turn to international synergies, just like the United States also did at the same time, but in this case not for the projection of power in space (Interkosmos program), but instead, in order to preserve its entity.

In the first decade of the 21st century, the Russian space program had restored its former glory, and had managed to foster a concrete joint effort with the West through the construction and operation of the ISS. However, the conflict in Georgia in 2008 formed the first (of the many later on) cracks on the relations of Russia with the West. In fact, the Russian space program has been suffering until today, from sanctions posed by the West as a consequence of the Russian invasions in Ukraine in 2014 and 2022. These sanctions have had significant implications to the Russian space industry which has been struggling to deliver new space hardware, nevertheless to keep the existing one in operation.

As the Russian Federation has been moving away from the major global powers during the war in Ukraine, it has turned to regional, and in some cases, isolated powers like Iran and North Korea to form alliances. Russia aspires to achieve its national goals, especially to prevail over Ukraine in the battlefield, and to combat technological deficits. In this context, the national security policies have gone anti-West, focusing on countering the Western advantages, especially the technological ones. Thus, Russia is focusing on anti-satellite weapons, electronic war and cyberattacks against Western infrastructure and tech companies like Starlink and Viasat. It is expected that unless the conflict in Ukraine is resolved, little of the above will change in the future. Unless a reapproach with China takes place, Russia will keep walking on the isolation path, and the technological gap with the West will possibly spread and Russia will enter the projected new space race with a handicap. Already the proposed Russian Orbital Station (ROS) after the abandonment of the lunar ambitions due to lack of funding, is an example of the possible fate of the Russian space program.

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